

Fungal Necrotizing Otitis Externa: A 14-Year Retrospective Study of Prognostic Factors

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ABSTRACT

ARTICLE DETAILS

Introduction:

Fungal necrotizing otitis externa (FNEO) is a rare but severe infection that predominantly affects immunocompromised individuals, particularly patients with diabetes mellitus. Compared with bacterial necrotizing otitis externa, FNEO is associated with greater diagnostic difficulties, delayed management, and more complex therapeutic strategies, often resulting in poorer outcomes.

Methods:

We conducted a retrospective study including 83 patients with microbiologically confirmed FNEO treated at the Military Hospital of Tunis between 2010 and 2024. Demographic, clinical, microbiological, radiological, therapeutic, and outcome data were collected and analyzed. Univariate and multivariate logistic regression analyses were performed to identify prognostic factors associated with unfavorable outcomes.

Results:

The mean age of patients was 59 years, and 73% had type 2 diabetes mellitus, among whom 63% had poor glycemic control (HbA1c > 8%). Otagia was present in all patients, facial nerve paralysis in 24%, and vestibular symptoms in 16%. The most frequently isolated fungal pathogens were *Candida albicans* (45%) and *Aspergillus* spp. (35%). Computed tomography revealed temporal bone osteitis in 68% of cases and extension to deep cervical spaces in 11%. Surgical intervention was required in 30% of patients, while 5% required admission to the intensive care unit. Overall mortality was 5%, and recurrence at six months was observed in 11% of cases. Multivariate analysis identified poor glycemic control (OR 2.8), facial nerve paralysis (OR 3.9), and deep tissue extension (OR 5.3) as independent predictors of poor prognosis.

Conclusion:

FNEO remains a life-threatening condition with outcomes strongly influenced by uncontrolled diabetes, cranial nerve involvement, and deep anatomical extension. Early diagnosis, strict glycemic control, and a multidisciplinary therapeutic approach are essential to improve patient prognosis. Further prospective studies are needed to optimize management strategies and reduce morbidity and mortality.

KEYWORDS: necrotizing otitis externa; fungal infection; diabetes mellitus; facial nerve paralysis; prognosis

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I. INTRODUCTION

Necrotizing external otitis (NEO) is a rare but potentially life-threatening infection, with reported mortality rates up to 20%. It is characterized by possible extension to the central nervous system and deep cervicofacial spaces, which complicates prognosis. NEO mainly affects vulnerable patients, including immunocompromised individuals, elderly patients, diabetics, and those with multiple comorbidities. In most cases, NEO is bacterial, with *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* responsible for 96–98% of infections [1].

An emerging fungal form of NEO (Fungal NEO, FNEO) has recently been described. FNEO poses diagnostic challenges and requires more complex management. Fungal infection should be suspected in patients with repeated negative bacterial cultures or lack of improvement under appropriate antibiotic therapy. The most commonly isolated fungi are yeasts of the *Candida* genus and molds such as *Aspergillus*. Current literature on FNEO is limited, mainly consisting of small case series. Consequently, the epidemiological profile and prognostic factors of FNEO remain poorly defined [2], and there is no consensus on the optimal therapeutic protocol. The aim of this study was to analyze the clinical and microbiological characteristics of patients with FNEO in our series and to identify factors influencing prognosis.

II. METHODS

This retrospective descriptive and analytical study included 83 patients diagnosed with fungal necrotizing external otitis. The study was conducted at the ENT and cervicofacial surgery department of the Military Hospital of Tunis, in collaboration with the Department of Parasitology and Mycology, between January 2010 and December 2024.

Inclusion criteria: Patients with microbiological confirmation of fungal infection, by either positive ear culture or positive *Aspergillus* serology.

Exclusion criteria: Purely bacterial NEO and incomplete medical records.

Data collection: Information collected included demographics and medical history (diabetes, immunodepression, prolonged corticosteroid therapy, chemotherapy), clinical signs at admission (otalgia, otorrhea, facial paralysis, vestibular symptoms), microbiological results (bacterial and fungal identification, antifungigram), paraclinical exams (laboratory tests, CT scan, MRI), treatment modalities (antibiotics, antifungals, surgery), and follow-up outcomes (clinical, radiological, biological).

Statistical analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 20. Qualitative variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages, and quantitative variables as mean \pm standard deviation. Patients were categorized into two groups based on outcome: favorable evolution and unfavorable evolution (severe complications, recurrence, or death). Univariate analysis used the Chi-square or Fisher's exact test for qualitative variables and Student's t-test for quantitative

variables. Variables with $p < 0.05$ in univariate analysis were included in a multivariate logistic regression to identify independent prognostic factors.

III. RESULTS

Eighty-three patients were included, comprising 54 men (65%) and 29 women (35%), with a mean age of 59 years (range 30–85 years). Most patients (73%) had type 2 diabetes, and 63% of these had poor glycemic control (HbA1c $> 8\%$). The mean duration of symptoms before consultation was 17 days (range 5–60 days). Clinically, otalgia was present in all patients (100%), purulent otorrhea in 89%, peripheral facial paralysis in 24%, and vestibular symptoms (vertigo or instability) in 16%.

A. Microbiological findings:

- Fungal infection alone: 40 cases (48%)
- Bacterial and fungal co-infection: 31 cases (37%)
- Bacterial infection alone: 11 cases (13%), subsequently reclassified as FNEO after fungal confirmation during follow-up

The most frequently isolated fungal agents were *Candida albicans* (45%) and *Aspergillus* spp. (35%). *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was the most common associated bacterium (40% of co-infections).

B. Imaging findings:

Computed tomography revealed temporal bone osteitis in 68% of patients, extension to deep cervical spaces in 11%, and labyrinthine involvement in 15% (**Figures 1 and 2**).

C. Treatment and outcomes:

All patients initially received adapted antibiotic therapy, followed by antifungal treatment after microbiological confirmation. Surgery was required in 25 patients (30%), and 4 patients (5%) were admitted to intensive care for severe complications. The mean hospital stay was 23 days. At 6-month follow-up, recurrence occurred in 9 patients (11%), and infection-related mortality was 5% (4 patients).

D. Prognostic factors:

Univariate analysis identified the following factors significantly associated with unfavorable outcomes:

- Poor glycemic control (HbA1c $> 8\%$): 52% in the favorable group vs. 83% in the unfavorable group ($p = 0.02$)
- Facial paralysis: 14% vs. 47% ($p = 0.01$)
- Extension to deep cervical spaces: 6% vs. 35% ($p = 0.004$)
- Diagnostic delay (>15 days): 38% vs. 63% ($p = 0.03$)

Multivariate logistic regression analysis results are summarized in **Table I**.

IV. DISCUSSION

Fungal necrotizing external otitis (FNEO) is a rare but severe infection, primarily affecting immunocompromised patients, notably those with diabetes mellitus or advanced age [1]. Clinically, FNEO shares many features with bacterial necrotizing otitis externa, making diagnosis challenging, particularly when bacterial cultures are repeatedly negative or empirical antibiotic therapy fails.

In our cohort, *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus* species were the predominant fungal agents, consistent with previous reports identifying these organisms as the main pathogens in FNEO [2]. The high prevalence of diabetes, especially with poor glycemic control (HbA1c > 8%), reflects the well-established link between hyperglycemia and impaired host defense. Hyperglycemia compromises neutrophil function and promotes fungal colonization, explaining its role as a negative prognostic factor in both univariate and multivariate analyses.

Peripheral facial paralysis occurred in nearly a quarter of patients and was strongly associated with unfavorable outcomes [3,4]. This complication reflects infection spreading to the facial nerve canal, indicating advanced disease. Similarly, extension to deep cervical spaces in some patients signifies more invasive FNEO, correlating with higher morbidity and mortality [5]. These findings reinforce the value of early detection of deep tissue involvement using imaging modalities such as CT and MRI [6].

Delayed diagnosis, defined as symptom duration exceeding 15 days, was also associated with worse outcomes [7]. This likely results from initial misidentification of the fungal infection or insufficient microbiological investigations, highlighting the need for high clinical suspicion, particularly in at-risk patients unresponsive to broad-spectrum antibiotics. Treatment of FNEO remains challenging due to the limited susceptibility of fungal pathogens to standard therapies and frequent bacterial-fungal co-infections [8]. Our approach—combining systemic antifungal therapy, adapted antibiotics, and surgical intervention when indicated—was effective in many cases, though some patients still experienced recurrences or complications.

The infection-related mortality rate of 5% in our series, although lower than in some previous cohorts, underscores the potential severity of FNEO. Recurrence at 6 months occurred in 11% of patients, emphasizing the importance of prolonged follow-up and, in some cases, extended antifungal therapy [9].

Multivariate analysis identified three independent prognostic factors: poor glycemic control, facial paralysis, and deep space extension. These factors should guide clinicians in intensifying monitoring and treatment in high-risk patients. Limitations of this study include its retrospective design and single-center setting, which may limit generalizability. However, the relatively large sample size and detailed clinical

and microbiological data provide valuable insights into the epidemiology and prognostic determinants of FNEO [10].

Future research should focus on prospective studies to better define optimal antifungal regimens, evaluate adjunctive therapies such as hyperbaric oxygen, and determine the benefits of early surgical intervention.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Fungal necrotizing external otitis is a serious infection, predominantly affecting diabetic and immunocompromised patients. Early diagnosis and differentiation from bacterial infections are essential to improve outcomes. Poor glycemic control, facial paralysis, and extension to deep cervical spaces are significant independent predictors of poor prognosis. Management requires a multidisciplinary approach, including systemic antifungal therapy, appropriate antibiotics, and surgical intervention when indicated. Close follow-up is important due to the risk of recurrence. Further studies are needed to establish standardized treatment protocols and improve patient survival. Awareness and timely intervention remain key to reducing morbidity and mortality in this challenging condition.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement: **Mtibaa Latifa:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft, Supervision. **Ferchichi Sana:** Data curation, Investigation, Writing – review & editing.

Ghorbel Syrine: Investigation, Data curation, Visualization.

Jemli Boutheina: Methodology, Resources, Validation.

Halwani Chiraz: Statistical analysis, Writing – review & editing. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Table I: Univariate and Multivariate Prognostic Factors

Prognostic Factors	Favorable Evolution (N=57)	Unfavorable Evolution (N=26)	p (Univariate)	OR (95% CI) Multivariate	p (Multivariate)
Poor glycemic control (HbA1c > 8%)	30 (52%)	22 (83%)	0.02	2.8 (1.0 – 7.9)	0.048
Facial paralysis	8 (14%)	12 (47%)	0.01	3.9 (1.1 – 13.9)	0.03
Extension to deep cervical spaces	3 (6%)	9 (35%)	0.004	5.3 (1.6 – 17.5)	0.006
Diagnostic delay (>15 days)	22 (38%)	16 (63%)	0.03	Not significant	Not significant

Figure 1. Non-contrast CT scan showing necrotizing external otitis, with thickening and obliteration of the external auditory canal (blue asterisk), associated with a lesion of the tympanic bone (red arrow) and extension close to the carotid canal (blue arrow), without evidence of fluid collection.

Figure 2: Contrast-enhanced axial T1 MRI demonstrates findings consistent with left necrotizing external otitis, with extension of the inflammatory infiltration into the infratemporal fossa (blue asterisk), parapharyngeal (red asterisk) and retropharyngeal spaces (blue arrow) and lateral pharyngeal wall (red arrow).